

Impact of online Education on the Mental Health and Physical Health of the Students (Raigarh, Chhattisgarh, India) during Covid 19 Pandemic

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Abstract: This research paper investigate how the online education during Covid pandemic effect the physical and psychological health of the students of Raigarh, Chhattisgarh, India. Covid 19 has caused destruction and devastation worldwide in the ways nobody can expect. The life of the people is totally changed and it affects the educational, social, emotional, economical, physical and psychological well being of the individual. During Covid -19 pandemic it is very challenging for the school administration, college administration, University of India and also for the Government of India how the teaching can be continuously going on without any interruption? But the challenge is how the classes will be taken whether from offline mode or online mode? There is also one question arouse in every one mind how the online teaching effective in learning process especially for students? And how its effect the mental health and physiological health of the students? To examine this study has been conducted on 450 students of Raigarh, Chhattisgarh India to know their views on how the online education has affected the psychological and physiological Health of the students. For this Kirodimal Government Arts and Science College, Raigarh Department of Psychology conducted a case study to investigate it. The finding of the study says that in positive and negative both the ways it affects the psychological and physical Health of the students.

Introduction

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Raigarh, Chhattisgarh India to know their views on how the online education has affected the psychological and physiological Health of the students. For this Kirodimal Government Arts and Science College, Raigarh Department of Psychology conducted a case study to investigate it. The finding of the study says that in positive and negative both the ways it affects the psychological and physical Health of the students.

Online education has drastically changed the way we study but the year and half of attending online classes from home have led to a string of Mental and physical health problems for both students and teachers. In this study students reported that due to online teaching they become 95.11% irritable, 100% stressful, 41.33% feeling depressed, 71.56% lack of interest in the studies, 97.56% feeling isolated, 66.88% socially deprived, 94.67% problem in concentration.

Table:1 Mental and Physical problems faced during covid 19 Pandemic during online teaching

S.No	Mental/ Physical problems faced during online teaching (total Sample size 450)	Total Participants reported	percentage
1.	Mental Fatigue	349	77.56
2	Depressed	186	41.33

3.	Anxiety	436	96.89
4.	Irritability	428	95.11
5.	Stressful	450	100
6.	Lack of Interest in studies	322	71.56
7.	Problem in concentration	426	94.67
8.	Feeling isolated	439	97.56
9.	Socially Deprived	301	66.88
10.	Pain in Back	386	85.78
11.	Eye problems	318	70.67
12.	Overweight	249	55.33
13.	Migraine/Headache	148	32.88
14.	Pain in Muscles	342	76.00
15.	Sleepness/Sleepy	386	85.78

Several research studies reported that overuse of technology can result in mental overload and disconnect people from nature, play and people. A child who spends too much time in virtual worlds is less likely to have effective social skills to interact in the real world simply from lack of practice. J. Kim, R. LaRose, & W. Peng, 2009 posited technology negatively impacted social skills. J. Y. Yen, C. H. Ko, C.F. Yen, H. Y. Wu & M. J. Yang, 2007 reported those engaging in excessive technology use have a decreased sense of time and concentration due to multi-tasking. In addition, they are not future-thinking and are more impulsive. Park & Hyun also found academic performance was affected more than any other factor.

Due to online teaching students may experience stress due to increased pressure to perform independent learning and abandoning their usual routines, which may lead to psychological consequences such as anxiety, depression, difficulty in sleeping and stress eating (Liu N, Zhang F, Wei C, Jia Y, Shang Z, Sun L, et al., 2020). Same thing we have found in the case studies students may experience stress, feel depressed and feel irritability and lack of concentration. Students also reported its affect their learning skill and cognitive abilities also. In this case study they may feel socially isolated and mental fatigue due to spend more time in online learning.

The exposure students receive during school days, interaction with teachers and the activities they organise and interaction with

peers all these things play an important role in shaping the personality of student. But with the major change in the mode of education students have lost this opportunity. Increased screen time have lead to unfavourable effects on the learning and psychological health of students. Fazean Idris, I N Zulkipli et al, 2021 Prolonged screen time have worsen the critical thinking ability of the brain. Students are trapped in their comfort zone and are unwilling to move out of it. Many of the students were involved in high risk behaviour like gambling and porn addiction. And also they spend a lot of time in video gaming and other such activities which may lead to mental retardation.

The online mode of teaching not only affect the psychological health of the students its also affect the physical health problems like eyesight problems, sudden weight loss or gain, back pain, migraine, fibromyalgia pain and so on. The students continuously sitting in the front of screen it may leads to strain on the eyes and resulting in major headaches. This was applicable not only to the students but also for the teachers. Its also leads to the lack of classroom ethics The posture, regularity, lack of routine, attentiveness has all resulted in health hazards. Constant sitting has caused weight concern as well. No physical activity has made the students restless and frustrated. This too took a toll on the eating habits, thus resulting in damage to the physical health. Some times studying online has resulted in poor/bad ergonomics, thus resulting in a lot of issues as

regards back pain. The results of the case study reported that 99% students reported that they have eyesight problems, 43% students reported severe headache due to continuously focus on the screen, 84% students reported that continuously sitting in the front of screen leads to back pain as well problem in cervicl region. The case study finding revealed that how the online mode of education affect their physical health as well as mental health.

Finally we concluded that Covid -19 outbreak has disrupted the lives of many people across the world the rapid increas in cases worldwide has created uncertainty and anxiety about what is going to happen. It has also Caused a tremendous level of stress among students. Distance learning is an acceleration of this exsisting challenges. Physical activity seem to be a factor that could prevent mental health disorders such as an anxiety, depression and irritability. These are just some of the challenges students are facing as a results of online education. Humans are resilient species and learn to adopt and evolved when we as a nation have been through a such a tough time and found a way to out of it. We can definitely learn to make

online learning more creative and enthusiastic. In the scenario of so many changes it is crucial to take care of our mental health and wellbeing by doing physical workout, meditation and yoga. Although it is traumatic experience of all but we have to take some preventive measures to test our capabalities to adopt to certain stressful and life threatening events.

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